

Dependence of Virtual Subjects Reflection from the features of Coping Behavior of Students

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II. PROCEDURE

Abstract—In the globalization process, when the struggle for minds and values of the people is taking place, the impact of the virtual space can cause unexpected effects and consequences in the process of adjustment of young people in this world. Their special significance is defined by unconscious influence on the underlying process of meaning and therefore the values preached by them are much more effective and affect both the personal characteristics and the peculiarities of adjustment process. Related to this the challenge is to identify factors influencing the reflection characteristics of virtual subjects and measures their impact on the personal characteristics of the students.

Keywords—coping behavior, overcoming, personalization (representation), psychological defense, values, virtual space, virtual subject, subjective reflection.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE concept of "virtual entity" is defined as "potentially manifested in the person of another" [1]. Having been in the inner world of man, virtual subject, in contrast to many other important, is highly significant for the subject, and therefore, often plays a decisive role in determining the behavior and activities [2]. Virtual entity, we can define as a significant introjects [3,4] and as an intimate personality of Frankl [5] The current virtual space is very different faces, and is presented as a positive or negative value systems. Important in this respect is the way young people express the virtual actors, what features of their personality and values they stand out. In this connection, the challenge is to identify factors influencing the reflection characteristics of virtual actors, and measures their impact on the personal characteristics of students. We assumed that the reflection characteristics of virtual actors, and students measure their impact depends on the characteristics of their coping system provides a stable relation of unconscious defensive strategies, and coping strategies.

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A. Methods

According to hypothesis following methods were used in the research: 1. Frydenberg, E., Lewis, R. Adolescent (Coping Scale - ACS), adapted by Krukova T.N.[6] "Scaling of regulatory and personal relations" Mislavskiy Y. A [7], technique of "Values of relations" developed by Tashimova F. S.[8]. Writing essays "My Hero". Data processing was carried out by factor analysis using "Principal Component" and object analysis and conducting content analysis.

Total of subjects 252 students.

B. Results

1st stage – Research on technique "Youth Coping Scale".

As the result there were 4 factors reflecting the ways of coping behavior that characterize the style to overcome difficult situations. Further the data were subjected to object which made it possible to define 4 groups of subjects with their characteristic coping strategies. Correlation of the strategies allowed to define styles of coping behavior of the students. On the basis of the objective analysis we had revealed 4 groups of students with characteristic styles of coping behavior. Group 1 – mobilization style – 25%; group 2 – productive style – 29%; group 3-emotionally focused style – 32%; group 4 – socially focused style – 14%.

Further the data received on a procedure locating attitude with virtual subjects have been subjected to the factor analysis. The analysis of results of virtual subjects reflection with which students cooperate indirectly, that is through Internet, has allowed to reveal four factors. The controlling factor of representatives of 1st group presented by following parameters: Provides pleasure (0,711); Stimulates aspiration to eccentricity (0,692); Stimulates initiative (0,648); Provides pride of oneself (0,599); Focus on popularity which is, self-growth (0,525); Stimulates work and spontaneity (0,501); Stimulates aspiration to surpass achievements of others, to compete (0,482); Stimulates capacity to accept positions and backgrounds of another (0,476); Stimulates freedom in choice (0,407); Stimulates independent considering a problem and decision-making (0,398); Focus on common egoism (0,393);

The controlling factor of representatives of 2nd group presented by following parameters: Focus on knowledge (0,622); Focus on the specific facts and a reality (0,587); Provides doubt in and shyness (-0,528); Stimulates aspiration to surpass achievements of others, to compete (-0,501); Stimulates the maximal disclosing capacities (0,497); Stimulates riskiness in the decision of vital problems (0,453); Stimulates aspiration to lead, "messages" behind oneself another (-0,483); Focus on care and the help (-0,476); Provides aspiration to co-work (0,432); Provides aspiration to completion of affairs « here and now » (0,394);

The controlling factor of students of 3rd group presented by following parameters: Stimulate capacity to accept positions and backgrounds of another (0,694); Stimulate confidence to another (0,645); Provide doubt in and shyness (0,632); Focus on self-improvement (0,591); Provides independence in decision-making (0,542); Stimulate adjustment of mutually beneficial attitudes (0,532); Provide difficulties in expression of the positions and stimulate a deepening in the private world (0,486); Focus on modesty, "great" business not for me (0,478); Assist caution in the decision of vital problems (0,437); Stimulate aspiration to material independence (0,412); Assist aspiration to surpass achievement of others, to compete (-0,409); Stimulate common egoism (0,370).

The controlling factor of representatives of 4th group presented by following parameters: Stimulates aggression and intolerance (0,670); Stimulate capacity to accept positions and backgrounds of another (-0,603). Stimulates aspiration to adjust mutually advantageous attitudes (-0,576); Stimulates aspiration to prove and defend the positions (0,527); Focus on self-improvement (0,504); Assist difficulty in expression of the positions and deepens in the private world (0,478); Stimulates aspiration to the maximal disclosing capacities (-0,469); Complicates freedom in choice (0,453);

How virtual subjects are presented? According to processing of the results received on the basis of a procedure by Mislavskiy J.A. In group 1 they are presented in as interesting, significant, stimulating claims and a high self-assessment and their information in relation with not only professional interest, but also with the broad audience of interests of examinees. Virtual subjects in group 2 represented—as significant, but distant on an image of "I" and another's. The works of authors connected with a profession. Virtual subjects are presented in group 3 – as distant, but worthy imitations and relatives on an image I. Interested authors not related with professional development. Virtual subjects are presented in group 4 as braking, forcing down and unworthy of imitations.

III. DISCUSSION

The analysis of parameters of students of group 1, allow to ascertain satisfaction of demands for the subject defining its creative adaptation to requirements of the modern life. In particular, it is possible to tell, that representatives of the given group, getting acquainted subjects of a virtual reality and ideas spent by them, reflect them as systems of readout to which it is necessary to correlate oneself. As a result of correlation, students of the given group show satisfaction in themselves and the capacities defining their eccentricity in the solving of vital problems. It is provided owing to correlation of the positions with author, stimulating work and spontaneity, the initiative, pride of oneself as capable to compete at higher level and to strengthen aspiration to glory and popularity.

The attitude with virtual subjects reflect not only their capacity to correlate and implant positions « I and the world », but also supports their aspiration to material independence. The given aspiration indissolubly related with the common

egoism which is bringing some doubt and shyness in own system. The analysis of the correlated demands allow to define sense of attitudes with virtual subjects as "self-satisfaction" or the "self-sufficiency", reflecting rather high level of the creative adaptation, as well as to aspiration to implant the of positions in relationships « I and the world ». The mechanism providing given sense, the creative identification defined by deep correlation and processing of system of values is.

In this connection, we can say that the relationship with the virtual subjects are, for this group, of high importance because they provide awareness of their own value in the world, as capable of creation, and to compete in the free world, which undoubtedly influences the perceived their self-sufficiency.

Analysis of the needs of students in Group 2, stimulated by virtual subjects can establish a sufficiently high differentiation value systems, "I and the world," providing in-depth analysis, maximizing the skills and responsibilities, in order to justify positions that cause doubt. That is, the virtual subjects are reflected as a stimulating review of their own values related to rooting (adaptation) value of other worlds, as a result of deep analysis and correlation with their. Virtual subjects in this group are of value. However, their importance is provided only from the point of view, cognition and self-improvement, is not associated with deep-seated emotional processes of identification and regulation of relations with the world. Correlation needs, allow us to determine the meaning of relationships with virtual subjects as "knowledge." Mechanism to ensure this sense, is a rational mechanism for identifying, reflecting the appropriateness of the relationship with the world.

Self-improvement can lead to realize of self-sufficiency of the subjects in the context of globalization, capable to the creation of new functional meaning, do not reject or suppress their own value system. New meanings are checked through the risky business entities, and provide material and spiritual freedom

Analysis of the needs of group 3 students, stimulated by virtual subjects, allow the adoption of state property without adequate processing and rationalized as the subjects of their choice. The lack of deep analysis, virtual subjects advertised values, make some doubt, provided by the underestimation of their own positions and their reevaluation in terms advertised, as they say the subjects of this group of "civilian" values. Various values of peace, aimed at both the positive and negative on the subjects of this group experimented in his own life. Values of peace prevail in qualitative terms of the values of the subject, giving rise to complex ions (fear of greatness and fame), providing a self-assessment of the subject, does not allow to provide not only competition but also the positions of equality, "I and the world." Values of the subject, as it were, absorbed by the global and all-powerful world in which the subject is dissolved. Unilateral commitment to global values, while ignoring their own positions are not conducive to feeling oneself and, therefore, difficult as self-expression and stimulate its own activity of the subject in his life, which provides an experience of loneliness and unhappiness.

Needs analysis, to determine the meaning of relationships with virtual subjects as "conformity." Mechanism to ensure this sense, is the emotional identification that reflects more of the external processes of assimilation, surface identification

with the world. The representatives of the group 3 - idols from the scope of western rock music, business, film, and the authors of online articles. This individual American actress Julia Roberts, the American illusionist David Copperfield, Olympic medalist Michael Phelps, Michael Jackson, etc. However, their representation reflects a superficial understanding of the hero. For example, the representation of Michael Jackson is characterized in terms of external appeal, the capacity for self-presentation, fortunate, successful, wealthy. But it did not reflect the Michael Jackson as the representative of science as a deep, mobile, creative person. Such a representation, of course, can stimulate the superficial system of values. This is a reflection of the virtual subjects are not able to update the understanding of the importance of himself, his own system of values determined by the functioning of the internal system of reference. The internal grid system works on a superficial level and cannot contribute to the disclosure of the deep reserve capacity. Another thing, when the same hero (Michael Jackson) is recognized as a fighter for equal rights as permanent self-affirming and creative person, squeezed in time of life. This representation can focus on the value of creative self-realization of man.

Analysis of the needs of group 4 students, stimulated by virtual entities can ascertain the state of aggression and rejection of the values promoted by them. This condition stimulates the desire to more deeply understand the system and realize their own values and attitudes, as well as their desire to defend and preserve. In this connection, is produced not only a distrust of virtual subjects, but also stimulated them to focus on negative information. The subjects of this group are characterized by the failure of permissiveness in human life, bare of sexual relations, ignoring the traditional humanitarian values of humanity. In this regard, members of the group attempts to isolate the system's own values and rejection advertised virtual actors. For members of Group 4 is characterized by an orientation to the idols of their own ethnic group.

Analysis of the system needs to determine the meaning of relationships with virtual actors as "aggressive." This meaning is determined by the mechanisms of exclusion, in particular the alienation and isolation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The obtained results revealed

1. A wide range of levels of perception and reflection by students of virtual subjects, from extremely positive to negative.
2. The dependence of the subjective reflection of the virtual world on the characteristics of coping behavior of students. It is established that productive coping styles (mobilization and harmonious) provide a positive reflection and a deeper differentiation of positive and negative factors of the virtual world, conscious processing of information and breaking it through their own values. Unproductive styles of coping (emotion-oriented and socially-oriented) or contribute to the negative reflection of the virtual world, amounting to the full exclusion and rejection (group 4) or the full adoption of the values of the virtual space without much reflection, which is fraught with "dissolution" in the virtual space.

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